

Enterprise environmental factors refers to any input or output system that is designed to identify and control aspects that have a significant impact on the outcome of the project, portfolio, or programme. This influence can either be positive or negative. Although this phrase isn't often used, it is important because most projects, if any, are affected by the environment they are placed in. If you find it difficult to access external resources and your project team is unable to meet the required capabilities, then this could be an indication of an enterprise environment issue.

They can refer to any elements the business must address, even industry laws, despite their title. The following are examples of environmental influences at work:

A. The organization's structure and culture

B. Industry or government norms

C. Existing human resources

D. Infrastructural components

E. Communication channels

F. Political climate

G. Market circumstance

H. Project management information system

Environmental influences in the workplace can be measured in a variety of methods, but adequate documentation is crucial. They are typically inputs, but learning about them is clearly a consequence of the project's beginning process. The project team may also have access to human resources. These resources can impact the company's environment. managers [site link](#) or the team should be aware of such factors even if they are not listed as an intake to a process group in the PMBOK.

Projects are often transient and are not always completed in isolation. Enterprise Environmental Factors and Organizational Process Assets have an impact on them when they are working in a controlled environment (OPA).

The project management information system , which is included in the environmental factors, gives users access to tools like service software, an approval system, a configuration control system, an information collection & distribution system, and interfaces to certain other online automated systems. This system can include automated data collection & reports on key performance indicators.

PMIS Software endorses Integration Management, Project Scope Management and Time Management. PMIS Software can also be hosted in the cloud or on-premises.

The PMIS is a collection of tools and processes that allow managers to deliver information. managers employ procedures and tools to gather, synthesize, and disseminate data via electronic & manual means. Upper & lower management use PMIS to communicate with one another.

The PMIS aids in the planning, execution, and completion of management objectives. Project managers utilize PMIS for budgeting and cost estimation during the planning process. The PMIS is also used to determine the scope baseline and create a specified schedule. The PMIS gathers information into a single database during the execution of project management goals. The PMIS is used to assess the baseline situation.

1. Scheduling and Planning

A PMIS could plan and compute the project's critical path and schedule, whether it was done using built-in scheduling tools or an interface to scheduling tools like Microsoft Project and Oracle Primavera P6. A PMIS would be able to set the scope baseline and construct or import a project's specific schedule.

2. Forecasting and Budgeting

A good PMIS will allow you to associate costs with specific tasks or components in order to make more accurate budget forecasts. To assess proper project progress and performance, a PMIS must include project cost estimating, forecasting, cost data, and schedule information. With all of this information in one place, expenses can be managed throughout the planning, estimating, and execution phases.

3. Procurement and Resource Management

A PMIS must be able to manage all aspects of procurement because resources and procured goods account for a significant portion of the project's costs and preliminary budget.

4. Project Management & Cost Control

A good PMIS will help project managers control costs and performance. They can update their plans and compare actual results to anticipated data changes. It also gives them what-if scenarios. All this while managing project modifications. Additional project values, such as planned value and real costs, can be calculated to show the project's current status & performance from a budget or schedule standpoint.

5. Reporting on Progress

Created project progress reporting saves project managers time while providing them with the tools they need to build and send reports suited to diverse audiences. Based on the data collected and processed, a PMIS can generate and share reports.

6. System and Data Integration

To eliminate data silos, PMIS must bring all project information together. PMIS should be compatible with other software and applications. This allows multi-project assessment and the bridging between systems and applications to obtain all information in one place.